

Generations & Gender Programme Belgium
GGP Belgium Paper Series - No. 4

GGG Wave 1 Belgium: Interview analysis

Inge Pasteels, Tom De Winter, Greet Lauwereys, Karel Neels

GGG

GGP BELGIUM PAPER SERIES – No. 4
GGS Wave 1 Belgium:
Interview analysis

Inge Pasteels

Tom De Winter

Greet Lauwereys

Karel Neels

Content

1	Preface.....	4
2	Introduction	5
3	Interview duration.....	6
3.1	Total interview duration.....	6
3.2	Interview duration by module.....	18
3.3	Interrupted and disrupted interviews.....	18
3.4	Learning effect of the interviewer	20
	Use of proxies	22
4	Presence & influence of non-proxies	25
4.1	Frequency of presence of non-proxies	25
4.1.1	In total survey.....	25
4.1.2	By module.....	26
4.2	Identity of present non-proxies	27
4.3	Influence of present others	28
4.4	Characteristics of influence	29
5	Language	30
6	Willingness to answer & Reliability of information	31
6.1	Willingness to answer	31
6.2	Reliability of information	32
7	Acceptance wave 2	33
8	Summary	35
	References.....	36

Figures

Figure 1: Total interview duration	7
Figure 2: Total interview duration by gender	8
Figure 3: Total interview duration by age	9
Figure 4: Total interview duration by education	10
Figure 5: Total interview duration by labour force status	11
Figure 6: Total interview duration by current partnership status	12
Figure 7: Total interview duration by parity	13
Figure 8: Total interview duration by region	14
Figure 9: Total interview duration by province (Flanders)	15
Figure 10: Total interview duration by province (Wallonia)	16
Figure 11: Summary statistics of the interview duration in minutes by module for all respondents ...	18
Figure 12: Time lag between the beginning and the end of the interview	19
Figure 13: Number of interrupted interviews by module	19
Figure 14: Total interview duration by intra-interviewer rank	20
Figure 15: Relationship between respondent and proxy (N=520)	22
Figure 16: Use of proxy, by NUTS1 region, age and sex	24
Figure 17: Frequency of presence non-proxy by module	26
Figure 18: Presence of others by module and NUTS1 region	26
Figure 19: Identity of present others	27
Figure 20: Influence by presence of others by module	28
Figure 21: Characteristics of influence (% of all those influenced)	29
Figure 22: Characteristics of influence (% of all interviews; N=7163)	30
Figure 23: Language of interview	30
Figure 24: Willingness to answer by NUTS1 region	31
Figure 25: Reliability of information by NUTS1 region	32
Figure 26: Participation to GGS Belgium, wave 2	33

Tables

Table 1: Summary statistics for total interview duration	6
Table 2: Total interview duration in minutes by gender	8
Table 3: Total interview duration in minutes by age	9
Table 4: Total interview duration in minutes by education	10
Table 5: Total interview duration in minutes by labour force status	11
Table 6: Total interview duration in minutes by current partnership status	12
Table 7: Total interview duration in minutes by parity	13
Table 8: Total interview duration in minutes by region	14
Table 9: Total interview duration in minutes by province (Flanders)	15
Table 10: Total interview duration in minutes by province (Wallonia)	16
Table 11: Multiple regression model with total interview duration as dependent variable	17
Table 12: Summary statistics of the interview duration in minutes by module for all respondents	18
Table 13: Total interview duration by intra-interviewer rank	20
Table 14: Reason for help or assistance	23
Table 15: Use of proxy by NUTS1 region	23
Table 16: Use of proxy, by NUTS1 region, age and sex	24
Table 17: Frequency of presence non-proxy by NUTS1 region	25
Table 18: Presence of others by module and NUTS1 region	27
Table 19: Willingness to answer by NUTS1 region	31
Table 20: Reliability of information by NUTS1 region	32
Table 21: Acceptance wave 2 by NUTS1 region, age and sex	34

1 Preface

Changing families and populations are presenting growing challenges for industrialized societies. As a result of low fertility levels prevailing for a long time, many countries are now expected to face labour shortages simultaneously with the demand to support a rapidly growing number of retired persons (UNECE, 2008). At the same time, younger generations tend to postpone marriage and parenting. Increased prevalence of consensual unions, decreasing stability of co-residential partnerships and the emergence of non-residential partnerships are other trends that can be seen in many countries (UNECE, 2008). Multifaceted family change requires that governments and other social partners monitor and, when necessary, step in to help families preserve and strengthen the ties that bind their members. To successfully meet these and other challenges, the UNECE Population Activity Unit launched the Generations & Gender Programme (GGP) to equip policy makers with a better understanding of the causes underlying recent developments and their consequences, with particular attention given to the relationships between children and parents (generations) and between partners (gender).

The GGP has two main pillars. The first is the system of national Generations & Gender Surveys (GGS), which are panel surveys of a representative sample of the 18 to 79 year-old resident population. The second is the set of Contextual Databases (CDB) that provide information on macrolevel factors influencing demographic trends. By pursuing a multidisciplinary and comparative approach, GGP reveals much more about demographic behaviours and offers explanations and solutions with respect to current demographic changes and their consequences. Fourteen UNECE countries and two countries outside the UNECE region are currently implementing GGP (UNECE, 2008).

GGP Belgium is part of the international programme launched by the UNECE Population Activities Unit. The implementation is financially supported by Belgian Science Policy within the AGORA-programme, Statistics Belgium (ADSEI/DGSIE), the Studiedienst van de Vlaamse Regering (SVR) and the Institut Wallon de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Statistique (IWEPS). The scientific team supporting GGP Belgium consists of researchers from the following research centres: Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Universiteit Antwerpen (UA), Universiteit Gent (UGent), Université Catholique de Louvain (UCL), Studiedienst van de Vlaamse Regering (SVR), Institut Wallon de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Statistique (IWEPS) and the Association pour le Développement de la Recherche Appliquée en Sciences Sociales (ADRASS).

United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, Population Activity Unit:
<http://live.unece.org/pau/ggp/welcome.html>

Generations & Gender Programme:
<http://www.ggp-i.org>

2 Introduction

In this paper we will put emphasis on data collection as a process and focus on the interview itself. For GGS computer assisted personal interview is chosen as data collection method. So we'll explore some characteristics of personal interviews in general and CAPI in particular.

Besides the absence of routing errors, the possibility to include automatic validity checks and appropriate questions formulations, automatic interviewer control is one of the well-known advantages of using CAPI as data collection method. The knowledge that the system accurately records information about the interview itself, e.g. time and duration of the interview, offers a protection against unwanted interviewer behaviour. In order to provide validity checks for the completed interviews, date and time were automatically recorded during the interview. Time and duration of interviews have been analysed continually during the fieldwork to implement permanent quality controls on the data collection process. In paragraph 1 of this paper we analyse the duration of the completed interviews of the final database.

Secondly, assistance by proxy respondents is explored. A proxy interview is an interview where the respondent has assistance of someone else for answering the questions. Individual respondents are randomly selected and only the individual selected for participation should be interviewed, but assistance by a proxy, if available, is allowed if difficulties with language, memory, ... hamper the interview.

In paragraph 3, we examine the presence of third persons during the interview. In the introduction of the questionnaire we forced the interviewer to advise explicitly against the presence of third persons. At the beginning of each module, the interviewer had to specify all present persons. If interviewer and respondent were not alone, the interviewer had to denote how much influence other people had on the respondent's answers.

A brief overview of languages used to conduct the interviews is given in a fourth paragraph. The GGS questionnaire was initially programmed in Dutch, French, English and German. Information for this analysis is obtained from the interview form.

In paragraph 5 respondent's willingness to answer and the reliability of the answers as evaluated by the interviewer in the interviewer form are discussed.

We end this paper by analysing the respondent's acceptance for wave 2. At the end of the interview the respondent was asked if he/she wanted to be contacted within three years. The answer of the respondents on this question is important because it has a legal implication: if the respondent refused to be contacted, the survey organization will be forbidden by law to ask for his/her participation in the second wave of this data collection project.

3 Interview duration

In this first section we will analyse the duration of the interview. The questionnaire was programmed as a computer assisted personal interview (CAPI) using Blaise 4.7 enterprise (Statistics Belgium) and Nipo CAPI Client 12.02.004.120 (TNS Dimarso) and was installed on a standard laptop computer. During the interview date and time were automatically recorded at the beginning of each module and at the end of the interview.

3.1 Total interview duration

The analysis of total interview duration is limited to 7013 or 98% of the interviews that are completed in one day. The remaining 150 or 2% of the completed interviews are interrupted and spread over several days. Information of these interrupted interviews is given in section 1.4.

Total interview duration of all interviews completed in one day varies between 14 and 781 minutes. The mean total interview duration in minutes is 73.19. We expect that the very long durations (such as 781 minutes) have been registered if the interviewer failed to close the CAPI-program at the end of the interview. Since detection of outliers caused by such technical failures is rather obviously, we analyse total interview duration by using univariate order statistics or we recoded it into a categorical variable for the bivariate analyses. Some univariate summary statistics are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary statistics for total interview duration

Total Interview Duration	
N	7013
Mean	73.19
St.dev.	31.04
Maximum	781
Minimum	14
Median	69
25th Pctl	57
75th Pctl	83

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 1: Total interview duration

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In order to explore more in depth the variation in total interview duration, we analyse this duration for different groups using a selection of crosscutting variables. In order to show graphically some results, total interview duration has been recoded into three categories: interviews with a short duration (less than 60 minutes), interview of medium duration (60-79 minutes) and long interviews that take 80 minutes or more. Between group comparisons are made by calculating different test statistics: Kruskal-Wallis (several groups) or Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon (two groups) if using the initial continuous time registration variable and χ^2 -teststatistics for the recoded variable. Graphs with corresponding tables and appropriate χ^2 -teststatistics are reported in this paper. No differences were found for several types of significance tests.

Figure 2: Total interview duration by gender

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 2: Total interview duration in minutes by gender

	men (N=3375)	women (N=3638)
<60 min.	28.33%	29.36%
60-79 min.	40.74%	41.51%
>79 min.	30.93%	29.14%
Chi²=2.77; df=2; p<.2494		
Median	69	69
P25	58	57
P75	84	82

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

The median total interview duration is equivalent for men and women. The quartile statistics P25 and P75 are lower for women than for men but all test statistics (only chi² is given in the table) show that there is no significant difference between the length of interviews for male or female respondents.

Figure 3: Total interview duration by age

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 3: Total interview duration in minutes by age

	Age					
	17-29 (N=1271)	30-39 (N=1264)	40-49 (N=1500)	50-59 (N=1333)	60-69 (N=959)	70-79+ (N=686)
<60 min.	38.16%	20.57%	21.8%	29.56%	33.37%	34.69%
60-79 min.	39.1%	45.97%	42.93%	39.46%	40.04%	36.88%
>79 min.	22.74%	33.47%	35.27%	30.98%	26.59%	28.43%
Chi²=168.97; df=10; p<.0001						
Median	65	72	73	69	67	66.5
P25	54	62	61	58	55	55
P75	78	85	86	83	82	82

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Results given in figure 3 and table 3 show that interviews with younger and older persons take less time than interviews with respondents between 30 and 59. Longest interviews are found especially for the age groups 30-39 and 40-49. We could expect that these interview take more time because of more complex household structures, labour force status, partnership history, ... than interviews of younger and older people.

Figure 4: Total interview duration by education

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 4: Total interview duration in minutes by education

	primary (N=863)	lower secondary (N=1341)	higher secondary (N=2357)	higher (N=2424)
<60 min.	33.6%	32.66%	29.1%	24.96%
60-79 min.	38.24%	39.37%	41.92%	42.53%
>79 min.	28.16%	27.96%	28.98%	32.51%
Chi²=39.24; df=6; p<.0001				
Median	67	69	69	71
P25	55	55	57	60
P75	82	82	82	85

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

The interviews of the higher educated people take more time than the interviews of the lower educated. One third of the interviews (33.60%) with the lowest educated people ended within an hour, only a quarter (24.96%) of all interviews with highest education people is limited to an hour. On the other hand, for almost a third of these highly educated respondents (32.51%) an interview takes longer than 80 minutes while only 28.16% of the respondents with only a primary educational level gives an interview of at least 80 minutes.

Figure 5: Total interview duration by labour force status

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 5: Total interview duration in minutes by labour force status

	employed (N=3954)	unemploye d (N=407)	student (N=358)	retired (N=1460)	non- active (N=834)
<60 min.	24.30%	31.20%	47.21%	35.48%	29.86%
60-79 min.	43.53%	38.08%	33.80%	39.32%	37.65%
>79 min.	32.17%	30.71%	18.99%	25.21%	32.49%
Chi²=141.79; df=8; p<.0001					
Median	71	70	61	66	69
P25	60	56	51	55	57
P75	84	85	75	80	85

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Longest interviews are registered for employees. The median duration of an interview with an employee is 71 minutes. Interviews with students and retired respondents are shortest, median durations are 61 respectively 66 minutes. Almost half of the interviews with students (47.21%) ended within an hour.

Figure 6: Total interview duration by current partnership status

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 6: Total interview duration in minutes by current partnership status

	married (N=3851)	cohabiting (N=929)	LAT (N=674)	single (N=1559)
<60 min.	25.68%	19.16%	24.93%	44.19%
60-79 min.	42.30%	46.61%	41.10%	35.02%
>79 min.	32.02%	34.23%	33.98%	20.78%
Chi²=255.08; df=6; p<.0001				
Median	70	73	72	62
P25	59	63	60	51
P75	84	85	85	76

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

If we compare total interview duration for different partner status, we find that interviews with respondents without co-resident or non-resident partner take less time. Married people conduct the interview more rapidly than cohabiting people and respondents with a LAT-relationship. Only 20% of interviews with single persons take longer than 80 minutes. Such long total interview durations are registered for one third of the interviews of all other respondents (married, cohabiting or having a LAT-relationship).

Figure 7: Total interview duration by parity

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 7: Total interview duration in minutes by parity

	No child (N=2324)	1 child (N=1380)	2 children (N=2001)	3 or more children (N=1308)
<60 min.	40.15%	27.25%	23.94%	18.04%
60-79 min.	38.55%	40.80%	44.28%	41.28%
>79 min.	21.30%	31.96%	31.78%	40.67%
Chi²=294.44; df=6; p<.0001				
Median	64	70	71	75
P25	53	58	60	63
P75	77	84	85	88.5

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Having more children increases the total duration significantly. People with 3 children or more spend on average 11 minutes more than respondents without children. Expanded household tables, questions about childcare, ... cause these increase.

Figure 8: Total interview duration by region

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 8: Total interview duration in minutes by region

	Brussels (N=620)	Flanders (N=3801)	Wallonia (N=2592)
<60 min.	20.00%	29.91%	29.44%
60-79 min.	36.45%	43.04%	39.47%
>79 min.	43.55%	27.05%	31.10%
Chi²=77.07; df=4; p<.0001			
Median	76	68	69
P25	64	57	57
P75	92	81	84

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Significant differences are found while analysing total interview duration by region. Longest interviews are registered in Brussels. Flanders has the lowest median interview duration. Also within Flanders and Wallonia, significant differences between provinces are found.

Figure 9: Total interview duration by province (Flanders)

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 9: Total interview duration in minutes by province (Flanders)

	Antwerpen (N=1013)	Limburg (N=530)	Oost- Vlaanderen (N=938)	Vlaams- Brabant (N=565)	West- Vlaanderen (N=755)
<60 min.	30.01%	22.83%	29.85%	31.86%	33.38%
60-79 min.	45.21%	40.75%	42.00%	46.55%	40.40%
>79 min.	24.78%	36.42%	28.14%	21.59%	26.23%
Chi²=43.41; df=8; p<.0001					
Median	67	73	68	66	68
P25	58	61	57	57	55
P75	79	85	81	78	81

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In Flanders, median duration varies from 66 to 73 minutes. Longest interview durations are registered in the province of Limburg.

Figure 10: Total interview duration by province (Wallonia)

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 10: Total interview duration in minutes by province (Wallonia)

	Brabant-Wallon (N=256)	Hainaut (N=967)	Liège (N=730)	Luxembourg N(=242)	Namur (N=397)
<60 min.	18.36%	24.82%	25.89%	29.75%	54.16%
60-79 min.	44.53%	41.37%	41.1%	31.82%	33.25%
>79 min.	37.11%	33.82%	33.01%	38.43%	12.59%
Chi²=167.75; df=8; p<.0001					
Median	73	71	70	73	58
P25	62	60	59	54	47
P75	89	86	85	88	69

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Analysis of total interview duration by province shows an outstanding distribution for the province of Namur. With a median total duration of 58 minutes, we conclude that interviews are very short in Namur compared with the other Walloon median interview durations varying from 70 to 73 minutes.

We end the analysis of total interview duration by performing a multiple regression model. Such model allows us to calculate the effect of a specific variable on total interview duration, controlled for other characteristics of respondents. Outliers are detected and excluded out of the analysis.

Table 11: Multiple regression model with total interview duration as dependent variable

Variable	Parameter		Standard Error	t Value	Pr > t
	DF	Estimate			
Intercept	1	63.39388	1.30379	48.62	<.0001
Gender (Men=refcat)					
Women	1	-1.38697	0.54135	-2.56	0.0104
Age (17-29=refcat)					
30-39	1	3.07651	0.99758	3.08	0.0021
40-49	1	3.16031	1.00346	3.15	0.0016
50-59	1	0.85080	1.04073	0.82	0.4137
60-69	1	3.15208	1.38962	2.27	0.0233
70-79+	1	5.01804	1.60250	3.13	0.0017
Education (Primary=refcat)					
Lower secondary	1	-0.31212	0.97025	-0.32	0.7477
Higher secondary	1	1.29865	0.92598	1.40	0.1608
Higher	1	2.81247	0.93682	3.00	0.0027
Labour force status (Employed=refcat)					
Unemployed	1	0.80659	1.17539	0.69	0.4926
Student	1	-2.03432	1.38903	-1.46	0.1431
Retired	1	-4.20139	1.18394	-3.55	0.0004
Non-active	1	-0.93993	0.92925	-1.01	0.3118
Current partnership status (Married=refcat)					
Cohabiting	1	4.23261	0.84768	4.99	<.0001
LAT	1	5.07980	1.01238	5.02	<.0001
Single	1	-4.13325	0.71938	-5.75	<.0001
Parity (No child = refcat)					
1 child	1	5.79499	0.80605	7.19	<.0001
2 children	1	6.63167	0.77428	8.56	<.0001
3 children or more	1	10.71339	0.85270	12.56	<.0001
Region (Flanders = refcat)					
Brussels	1	9.30832	0.96089	9.69	<.0001
Wallonia	1	2.29352	0.56456	4.06	<.0001
R-Square = 0.0758 (N=6964)					

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Most effects of the bivariate analyses for variables shown in figure 2 till figure 8, are still significant after controlling for all covariates. Additionally we see that interviews with female respondents tend to be shorter than interviews with male respondents. Only 7.5% of the variance is explained by the model. We assume that including characteristics of interviewers could improve significantly the fit of the model.

3.2 Interview duration by module

Table 12: Summary statistics of the interview duration in minutes by module for all respondents

Module	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Median	11	4	4	6	4	7	4	6	3	4	11
P25	9	1	3	4	1	6	3	4	2	3	9
P75	14	6	8	8	7	8	5	9	5	6	14
Mean	13.06	4.63	6	6.2	4.11	7.54	4.53	7.08	3.35	4.64	12.29
St.dev.	18.6	5.26	4.8	5.07	3.72	9.04	2.38	4.13	2.67	2.37	10.49

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 11: Summary statistics of the interview duration in minutes by module for all respondents

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 11 shows that the first and the last module take more time than all other modules. Furthermore, we can distinguish the modules with more and less variety with respect to interview duration. Module 6,7, 9 and 10 are rather homogeneous while a more varying interview duration is registered for module 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8 and 11.

3.3 Interrupted and disrupted interviews

As already said in section 1.1, 150 or 2% of all interviews are interrupted and spread over several days. Almost two third of these interviews (N=105) are completed within 7 days and another 37 interviews are continued within a month after the interruption. The remaining 8 interviews are continued after more than a month. For these interviews the interval between the start of the interview the first time and the end of the interview is between 32 and 109 days. Figure 12 shows the time lag between the beginning and the end of the interview.

Figure 12: Time lag between the beginning and the end of the interview

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Two third (N=100) of all interruptions are registered in module 1. We could expect that this interruption is mainly caused by computer manipulations of the interviewer preparing the interview. Some of them make sure that all information needed for the interview is available on the laptop, by starting all interviews before they visit the respondent. The number of interruptions for the other modules are given in figure 13.

Figure 13: Number of interrupted interviews by module

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

The disrupted interviews are not included in the final dataset.

3.4 Learning effect of the interviewer

In this section we analyse the total interview duration according to the number of interviews an interviewer did for GGS. We assume that the first set of 5 interviews takes more time than the other interviews. We think that the experience of the interviewer with reading the screens and questions of this specific CAPI-survey for GGS decreases the total interview duration after some interviews. To test this hypothesis we compare total interview durations of interviews of rank 1 to 5 with interviews of higher order ranks for interviewers who conducted more than 5 interviews.

285 of the 337 GGS-interviewers collected more than 5 interviews. The analysis of the learning effect of the interviewer is made on their interviews.

Figure 14: Total interview duration by intra-interviewer rank

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 13: Total interview duration by intra-interviewer rank

	intra-interviewer rank	
	1-5 (N=1388)	>5 (N=5479)
<60 min.	18.08%	31.99%
60-79 min.	38.76%	42.05%
>79 min.	43.16%	25.95%
Chi²=187.68; df=2; p<.0001		
Median	76	67
P25	64	56
P75	92	80

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 14 and table 13 show that the total interview duration decreases after the first set of 5 interviews. The median duration is 10 minutes lower for the interviews ranked beyond 5. 43.16% of the interviews with intra-interviewer rank 1 to 5 takes 80 minutes or longer. Such long durations are registered only for a quarter of the interviews with higher rank. On the other side, almost one third of these interviews (31.99%) ended within an hour, while only 18.08% of the interviews ranked 1 to 5 were completed in less than 60 minutes.

Use of proxies

A majority of the interviews was executed without proxy, i.e. any help or assistance of someone else than the interviewer and the respondent. Only in 7.3% (525) of the cases the interviewer reported some degree of help or assistance by a proxy.

In most of these cases, 91.4% (476), the help or assistance was provided by a member of the respondent's household. In 8.6% (44) the helper was not a member of the household of the respondent.

Figure 15: Relationship between respondent and proxy (N=520)

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – calculations by authors

Figure 15 shows how the respondent and the helping or assisting household member is related to each other. In the large majority (75%) of the cases with a proxy, the proxy is the (cohabitating of non-cohabitating) partner of the respondent. All other categories are much more rare: biological child, biological parent, friend, brother, sister (in the 'other'-category),

In table 14 the reasons for the use of a proxy are given. More than one reason were allowed per interview. More than half of those using a proxy (54.1%) gives another reason than those provided in the answer categories. We do however have no information about what this reason may be. The other most chosen categories are memory reasons (22.7%) and language reasons (15.2%).

Table 14: Reason for help or assistance

	% of those being assisted (N=525)
Health	7.4%
Memory	22.7%
Language	15.2%
Expression	6.5%
Hearing	1.9%
Psychic	3.2%
Other	54.1%

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – calculations by author – more than one reason possible per respondent

We also test whether the use of proxies was influenced by NUTS1 region¹, age and sex.

Table 15: Use of proxy by NUTS1 region

	Yes	No	N
Brussels	10.50%	89.50%	679
Flanders	5.60%	94.40%	3855
Wallonia	9.20%	90.80%	2620

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – calculations by author

The percentages for Brussels and Wallonia are not significantly different. The percentage for use of proxies in Flanders however is significantly lower (Model Chi²: 40.236, df.:2; p>.001) compared to the other regions.

In table 16 the percentages in use of proxies are given separately for men and women and the two age groups (18-44 and 45-79) in the three regions. Based on a logistics regression (Model Chi²=107.295; df=4; p<.001) including region, age groups and sex, we find confirmation for the fact that the use of proxies is significant lower in Flanders in comparison with Wallonia and Brussels (p<.001). We also find that older respondents (45-79) have a significant higher probability to make use of a proxy compared to the younger respondents (18-44) (p<.001). And male respondents tend to have a significant higher chance (p<.001) of using a proxy compared with female respondents. The differential chances for use of proxy are visually presented in figure 16.

¹ NUTS stands for 'Nomenclature of Units for Territorial Statistics'. It is a standard developed by Eurostat to subdivide countries hierarchically in regions of three levels. In Belgium three first-level (NUTS1) regions are defined: Flanders, Brussels and Wallonia. More information on NUTS can be found on: http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/nuts_nomenclature/introduction

Table 16: Use of proxy, by NUTS1 region, age and sex

		Yes	No	N
Flanders	Men, 18-44	5.50%	94.50%	796
	Women, 18-44	2.80%	97.20%	925
	Men, 45-79	9.00%	91.00%	1062
	Women, 45-79	4.50%	95.50%	1072
Brussels	Men, 18-44	8.60%	91.40%	174
	Women, 18-44	8.10%	91.90%	173
	Men, 45-79	14.10%	85.90%	149
	Women, 45-79	11.50%	88.50%	183
Wallonia	Men, 18-44	7.30%	92.70%	550
	Women, 18-44	4.90%	95.10%	635
	Men, 45-79	13.00%	87.00%	700
	Women, 45-79	10.60%	89.40%	735

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 16: Use of proxy, by NUTS1 region, age and sex

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

4 Presence & influence of non-proxies

In the previous chapter the use of proxies was discussed: proxies were present during the interview to help the respondent to answer the questions. However it happens that there are people present who do not have the intention to assist or help the respondent, although they have some degree of influence on the interview. In this paper, we call them non-proxies.

4.1 Frequency of presence of non-proxies

4.1.1 In total survey

Table 17: Frequency of presence non-proxy by NUTS1 region

	Never	In some modules	In all modules	N
Flanders	68.0%	23.8%	8.2%	3860
Brussels	70.1%	20.1%	9.7%	680
Wallonia	66.8%	24.0%	9.2%	2623

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 17 presents the percentages of interviews with no presence of others during the interview at all, those with a person present during some modules and those interviews with someone present during all the modules of the interview. The distribution is for the three regions very similar, with most of the interviews done without someone else present except the interviewer and the respondent (68% in Flanders, 70.1% in Brussels and 66.8% in Wallonia). In 20-25% of the cases someone extra was present during a number of modules: 23.8% in Flanders, 20.1% in Brussels and 24% in Wallonia. Only in a minority of the interviews someone was present during the total interview: 8.2% in Flanders, 9.7% in Brussels and 9.2% in Wallonia. A chi-square test confirmed no significant differences between them ($\chi^2=7.169$; $df=4$; $p=.127$).

4.1.2 By module

Figure 17: Frequency of presence non-proxy by module

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In figure 17 for each module the percentage of interviews that was executed with a non-proxy present is presented. Especially for module 9 concerning activities and incomes of the partner of the respondent, we see a somewhat higher percentage. However differences between modules are rather small.

Figure 18: Presence of others by module and NUTS1 region

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Table 18: Presence of others by module and NUTS1 region

	Flanders			Brussels			Wallonia		
	Yes	No	Total	Yes	No	Total	Yes	No	Total
M1	19.4%	80.6%	3860	22.9%	77.1%	680	21.3%	78.7%	2622
M2	18.8%	81.2%	3860	21.0%	79.0%	680	21.4%	78.6%	2623
M3	20.5%	79.5%	3860	20.9%	79.1%	680	22.5%	77.5%	2623
M4	20.1%	79.9%	3860	21.5%	78.5%	680	23.0%	77.0%	2623
M5	19.5%	80.5%	3860	19.9%	80.1%	680	22.6%	77.4%	2623
M6	19.7%	80.3%	3860	20.4%	79.6%	680	22.8%	77.2%	2623
M7	19.9%	80.1%	3860	20.0%	80.0%	680	23.5%	76.5%	2623
M8	19.7%	80.3%	3860	20.4%	79.6%	680	22.5%	77.5%	2623
M9	22.8%	77.2%	3082	24.2%	75.8%	472	25.5%	74.5%	1975
M10	20.3%	79.7%	3860	20.7%	79.3%	680	23.9%	76.1%	2623
M11	20.6%	79.4%	3860	20.9%	79.1%	680	23.9%	76.1%	2623
Total	20.1%	79.9%	100.0%	21.2%	74.3%	100.0%	23.0%	77.0%	100.0%

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In figure 18 and table 18 the percentages of the interviews that were executed with a non-proxy present are shown. The results are on average very similar for the three NUTS1 regions.

4.2 Identity of present non-proxies

Figure 19: Identity of present others

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 19 shows for each module separately the percentage of the presence of the partner, a child under 6, a child above 6 or another person for all those where a non-proxy was present. If someone is present during the interview, it is in a vast majority of the cases the partner of the respondent (around 70%). Presence of children or other individuals is much lower. The distribution is rather equal across the modules, except for module 9. Module 9 contains questions about the partner's activities and incomes.

4.3 Influence of present others

After each module, for those who reported the presence of others during that module, it was asked to what degree the interviewer experienced influence of these present others on the respondents answers. A four-step answer scale from 'totally no influence' to 'very much influence' was provided.

Figure 20: Influence by presence of others by module

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

Figure 20 shows some variation of the influence between the modules in the GGS questionnaire. The strongest influence was experienced for module 9, the module on the partner's activities and income. On the second place we have module 4, on the household. This module includes topics such as the division of the household tasks.

4.4 Characteristics of influence

Figure 21: Characteristics of influence (% of all those influenced)

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In figure 21 the characteristics of the influence by non-proxies is presented as percentages of all those that were influenced. We see that in general 'the other person responds instead of the person' and 'the respondent hesitates' are most frequently mentioned, the other answer categories have only marginal percentages. The distribution in percentages also varies between the modules. We see for example that 'the other proxy responds instead of the respondent' is much more given as answer for module 2 (organization household) and 9 (partner's activities and income). These higher percentages coincide with lower percentages for 'the respondent hesitates'.

Figure 22: Characteristics of influence [% of all interviews; N=7163]

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In figure 22 the same characteristics of influence are given, this time as percentages of all interviews. Then it becomes clear that this influence by non-proxies is only a marginal phenomenon with all percentages lower than 4%. In general we see similar trends as in figure 21.

5 Language

The CAPI was available in Dutch, French, English and German. 53.1% of the interviews were conducted in Dutch, 46.0% of the interviews in French. 15 interviews (0.2%) were conducted in English and 25 in German (0.4%) (Figure 23). Six interviews were conducted in a language that was not provided in the CAPI. These languages are Spanish, Greek, Italian, Moroccan, and Russian.

Figure 23: Language of interview

	Flanders		Brussels		Wallonia		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Dutch	3762	97.70%	34	5.00%	11	0.40%	3807	53.20%
French	82	2.10%	639	94.10%	2574	98.20%	3295	46.10%
English	8	0.20%	3	0.40%	4	0.20%	15	0.20%
German	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	28	1.10%	28	0.40%
Other language	0	0.00%	3	0.40%	3	0.10%	6	0.10%
Total	3852	100.00%	679	100.00%	2620	100.00%	7151	100.00%

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

6 Willingness to answer & Reliability of information

6.1 Willingness to answer

The interviewers were asked for each interview to which degree the respondent had been willing to answer during the interview, on a scale from 0 (not willing) to 10 (very willing). In figure 24 the distribution of these scores is presented for each NUTS1 region.

Figure 24: Willingness to answer by NUTS1 region

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In table 19 the mean and standard deviation for the NUTS1 regions are given. A ANOVA test with Bonferroni post-hoc test confirms that the means of all three regions are significantly ($p < .001$) different. So in Flanders interviewers estimate the willingness of the respondents to answer the highest, followed by Wallonia and Brussels.

Table 19: Willingness to answer by NUTS1 region

	Valid N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Flanders	3845	9.17	1.001
Brussels	679	8.80	1.031
Wallonia	2620	9.06	1.036

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

6.2 Reliability of information

At the end of each interview the interviewer is also asked to evaluate the reliability of the answers given by the respondent. This reliability is expressed on a scale from 1 to 10, with 1 very low and 10 very high. Figure 25 shows the distribution of this variable.

Figure 25: Reliability of information by NUTS1 region

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

In table 20 the means and standard deviation for Belgium and the NUTS1 regions are given. An ANOVA test with Bonferroni post-hoc test confirms that only the mean score of Brussels differs significantly from Flanders and Wallonia. So the interviews in Brussels are evaluated significantly less reliable than those in Flanders or Wallonia. However the means are still very high. Even the score in Brussels is still very good.

Table 20: Reliability of information by NUTS1 region

	Valid N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Belgium	7144	8.91	1.137
Flanders	3845	8.97	1.087
Brussels	679	8.53	1.471
Wallonia	2620	8.93	1.090

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

7 Acceptance wave 2

Figure 26: Participation to GGS Belgium, wave 2

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

The respondent was asked if he/she wanted to be contacted for wave 2. Very important is that it was made clear that this question is only a question about recontacting the respondent, and not any commitment to really participate in wave 2. It was even explicitly mentioned that if they would say yes now, they still can refuse to participate in wave 2 when they are actually contacted then. The answer of the respondents on this question has also a legal implication: if the respondent said no, the survey organization is forbidden by law to recontact the person for wave 2.

A large majority, more specifically 6771 of the 7163 respondent gave a positive answer on this question. This is 94.5%. So only 5.5% (392 respondents) indicated that they preferred to be not contacted anymore. Based on a logistic regression model, the percentage for participation to wave 2 was not significantly different between age groups (18-44, 45-79) or male and female respondents. However region makes a significant ($p < .001$) difference. Although the percentages of those willing to be recontacted for wave 2 for Flanders and Wallonia are very similar, respectively 96.5% (3726 of 3860) and 95.2% (2498 of 2623), the percentage in Brussels is much lower with only 80.4% (547 of 680).

Based on a logistics regression model, we have found that the differences in acceptance of wave 2 recontacting is significantly different for all three regions. So the acceptance is the highest in Flanders, followed closely by Wallonia and the lowest for Brussels.

Table 21: Acceptance wave 2 by NUTS1 region, age and sex

		Yes	No	Total
Belgium	Men, 18-44	93.6%	6.4%	1522
	Women, 18-44	95.1%	4.9%	1734
	Men, 45-79	94.6%	5.4%	1913
	Women, 45-79	94.7%	5.3%	1994
Flanders	Men, 18-44	95.4%	4.6%	797
	Women, 18-44	97.5%	2.5%	925
	Men, 45-79	96.2%	3.8%	1063
	Women, 45-79	96.8%	3.2%	1075
Brussels	Men, 18-44	81.7%	18.3%	175
	Women, 18-44	81.5%	18.5%	173
	Men, 45-79	82.6%	17.4%	149
	Women, 45-79	76.5%	23.5%	183
Wallonia	Men, 18-44	94.9%	5.1%	550
	Women, 18-44	95.3%	4.7%	636
	Men, 45-79	94.6%	5.4%	701
	Women, 45-79	96.1%	3.9%	736

Source : GGS Belgium, Wave 1 – Calculations by authors

8 Summary

In this paper we analysed some characteristics of the interview process. This summary resumes some conclusions.

The median total interview duration of the completed interviews is 69 minutes. 2% of all interviews are spread over several days. Longest interviews are recorded for respondents between 30 and 49 years old, for highly educated people and for the employed. Also interviews with cohabiting people and respondents with a LAT-relationship take more time than interviews with single or married persons. Flemish interviews are shorter than interviews conducted in Wallonia or in Brussels.

Only 7.3 % of the respondents needed some assistance by a proxy. Most of this assistance (73.3%) was given by the partner of the respondent. In 21% of the interviews, other people than the respondent were present during the interview. Their influence was minimal and most of the time evaluated as 'not at all' by the interviewer.

53.2% of all interviews was conducted in Dutch, 46.1% were French-speaking respondents. For 15 interviews, the English version of the CAPI is used and 28 respondents preferred the German questionnaire.

The willingness to answer of the respondent as well as the reliability of the information are evaluated by the interviewer. On a scale from 1 to 10, the mean willingness to answer is 9.17 in Flanders, 9.06 in Wallonia and 8.80 in Brussels. On a scale with range 1 to 10, the reliability of the information is 8.91 on average for all interviews.

Finally, 94.5% of all respondents agreed with the idea of being contacted for wave 2. So, 6771 respondent can be invited to participate in a follow-up interview.

References

Fuchs, M., Couper, M. & Hansen, S. (2000). Technology Effects: Do CAPI or PAPI interviews take longer? *Journal of Official Statistics*, 16 (3), pp.273-286.

UNECE (2008) What UNECE does for you. ... UNECE works on the generations and gender programme, Geneva, UNECE.

Statistics Belgium economie

Vlaamse Regering

